

THE INFLUENCE OF MODIFIER ELEMENTS ON THE MICROSTRUCTURE OF AlSi ALLOY DESTINED FOR MATRIX OF COMPOSITES WITH SiC AND C PARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

In presented work the influence of modifier elements such as Ti, B, Sr and Mg on microstructure of hypoeutectic AlSi7Mg alloy designed as matrix of composites reinforced by SiC and C_g particles were presented. The alloying elements were selected based on their effects and suitability for modification of aluminium alloy matrix composite microstructure and properties. On the basis of structural studies carried out by means an optical and scanning electron microscope significant effect on the grain refinement of the alloy microstructure and improving the wetting conditions between matrix and reinforcement were described.

1 INTRODUCTION

Presently the aluminium - silicon alloys and composite materials based on its matrix have found many industrial applications especially in the automotive industry [1]. Particularly the cast hybrid composites (e.g.: Al/SiC_p+Cg_p or Al/SiC_p+GR_p) have great potential to be applied as structural and functional materials in the future [2-5]. The basic and economical methods for the production of metal matrix composites are based on the liquid-phase processes (e.g.: mechanical stirring [2], die casting, infiltration). For all casting processes the aluminium matrix alloy should be characterized by high strength, possibility to heat treatment and good technological properties (high castability, good wettability on surface reinforcement and low viscosity). These properties can be obtained through addition of proper alloying elements [6]. The alloying elements may be classified as major elements (Si, Cu, Mg), minor elements (Ni, Sn), microstructure modifiers elements (Ti, B, Sr, Be, Mn, Cr) and impurity elements (Fe, Zn) [6,7].

2 MATERIALS, METHODS AND RESULTS

The EN AC-AlSi7Mg (AK7) was used as a metallic matrix and its chemical composition in initial state has been shown in Table 1. The matrix alloy composition was selected from the point of view of the aluminium hybrid composite suspension production (Al/SiC_p+Cg_p). Selected alloying additives, Mg and Sr and also Ti and B used for aluminium alloy modification. The structure of Al alloy before and after modification was observed using light microscopy [Fig.1].

	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Ti	Sr	B
ENAC-AlSi7Mg	6,3	0,462	0,0184	0,126	0,385	0,0412	0,0025	0,0064

Table 1: The chemical composition of initial Al alloy.

Figure 1: AlSi7Mg alloy microstructure in initial state.

The AlSi7Mg base alloy has been melted and in the next step of process it has been modified by 2wt. % Mg and 0.03 wt % Sr [7]. The Mg (magnesium) to improve wettability of the ceramic particles surface by the liquid alloy was added. In turn Sr (strontium) in aim of modify the morphology and structure of the silicon phase but first of all to obtain favorable condition for connection of reinforcement particles with matrix alloy. Effect of Mg and Sr additives evaluated based on results composite microstructure observation by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

Figure 2: AlSi7Mg2Sr0.03/SiC_p+C_p composite microstructure: (a) LM micrograph showing the distribution of ceramic particles and (b) surface distribution of elements, SEM.

Another solution is modification of aluminium alloy by titanium and boron addition. In this case, is expected to the grain refining and improved strength properties of Al matrix. Influence of such modification on the alloy microstructure was evaluated based on the results of the measurement interdendritic distance (DAS). Software LUCIA-Dendrites 6.0 for measuring of secondary dendrite arm spacing was used.

	DAS _{AVG} [μm]
AlSi7Mg	9,11
AlSi7Mg + TiB	8,97

Table 2: The results of secondary dendrite arm spacing evaluation.

Figure 3: Microstructure of AlSi7Mg alloy modified by 0.1 wt. % Ti and 0.01 wt % B alloying additions.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Presented investigations were confirmed that the known modifiers for aluminum alloys are also useful for the preparation of composite suspensions. However selection of alloying elements must be based on their suitability for concrete purpose.

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